

Assessing the Effect of Past and Present Land Use on Physical Landscape at Cooper's Hill Slopes, Egham, Surrey

Abstract

This research paper investigates the past and present land-use on Cooper's Hill slopes, and analyses future land management options. Cooper's Hill is a relatively small town slightly north of Egham, and in the southeast of England. The slopes studied are provided by the National Trust as a part of a protected and walkable area making up the greater Runnymede floodplains of the Thames River.

Collating evidence from survey and analysis of Cooper's Hill slopes, this research demonstrates that Cooper's Hill slopes has experienced both physical and chemical changes to the land due to both human and environmental factors which effect land-use. The collected data depicts the past and present landscape of the slopes, including frequency and magnitude of those changes, and how humans might have effected these changes.

Main

The research of Cooper's Hill Slopes (CHS) is not only important, but necessary to understand past and present risks, which will affect the future. Cooper's Hill, see Figure 1, has seen many owners such as the Priory of Ankerwyke in 1160, a Lord of Windsor in 1530, and has seen 3 Universities throughout much of the late 1800's to present (Egham Museum). The slopes have been owned by The National Trust (NT) since 1983, and are part of the river Thames floodplain, along with Runnymede and Egham (NT Heritage Records). Consequently, CHS and surrounding areas of Egham, see figure 2, are no strangers to the Thames. In the winter of 2013/14, the river broke its banks and flooded Egham, see Figure 1, (Palmer 2023). This will only increase under the IPCCs 2007 predictions, see Figure 2, which show a 15% estimate increase in precipitation in Egham area during the winter months. The IPCC also reported an increase in temperature during Britian's hottest months of the year, contributing to heatwaves. Faratin (2023) discusses the heatwaves which affected Britain in July of 2022, and subsequently caused 40C in some places. While these climate factors will probably push people out of Egham and CHS, other developments like the addition of a runway at Heathrow, could bring more people to the area (Palmer 2023). The need for additional housing for those workers necessary at an enlarged Heathrow, and scarcity of housing in closer areas, such as Egham, due to flooding. As well as eutrophication of the

Thames, therefore endangering human health, could all contribute to a movement of people to higher, and safer grounds like CHS.

The aim of this report is to assess the impact of past and present land-use change on Cooper's Hill Slopes, Egham, Surrey to inform future land use strategies.

Objectives to complete this, consist of locating the area including sampling locations; providing context to the importance of the report, detailed explanation of experiments undertaken, report results, discuss past land use, followed by present land use, frequency and magnitude of both past and present land-use changes, and finally, conclude how land-use has altered CHS with future predictions.

Figure 1: Cooper's hill slopes close-up

CHS Surrounding Areas

Figure 2: CHS surrounding areas

Figure 3: 2014 Flooding of Egham

Figure 4: IPCC 2007 climate report Europe estimates

Methods

Method	Purpose	Equipment	Sampling Location	Sampling Strategy	Limitations
Land Surveying	Describe and map physical area of sampling site	Abney level, total station, compass	Cooper's Hill Slopes Group 1 Quadrat B	Random	Abney level accuracy, total station reliance on satellites
Vegetation Surveying	Describe vegetation frequency density and count of sampling site	Tape measure, vegetation leaf identifier	Cooper's Hill Slopes Group 1 Quadrat B	Random	Human error misidentification, and height estimates
Soil Surveying	Describe soil qualities of sampling site	Penetro-meter, shovel, hand auger	Cooper's Hill Slopes Group 1 Quadrat B	Random and systematic	hand auger restricts depth sampling ability
Pollen Analysis	Observe pollen concentration and frequency	Micro-scope, pollen identification chart	Meadlake, Egham	Random and systematic	Human error misidentification, and sampling bias
Water Analysis	Observe physical and chemical local water qualities	'Paqualab', pH meter, dissolved oxygen meter, conductivity meter	Langham pond, river Thames, Egham tap water (see Figure 10)	Random	Human error, machine error, no recent weather disturbances

Table 1: Which experiments were completed and how they were accomplished

Results

Land surveying allowed for creation of elevation points throughout CHS (refer to Table 4, 5, 6, and 7 in appendix), to be created into a contour map (see Figure 5). The map shows general location in relation to landmarks such as the Air Force Memorial and Runnymede, as well as relation to other sampling locations like Langham Pond, Thames River, and Mead Lake. Though quadrat B is located off map, it is shown in larger scale on bottom left in greater description, including points of interest.

Vegetation surveying allowed for frequency of each tree species to be calculated (refer to Table 8 in appendix) (see Figure 6). An overwhelming majority, at over 50% of trees on CHS, were field maple/sycamore, followed only by ash/rowan at nearly 30% and oak at a mere 6%. Hazel, birch, hawthorn/blackthorn species are of little significance, and no fir, elm, or yew species were documented. Although they are included in the figure, Ash trees in the area many carry the blight, and the National Trust is required to fell infected individuals (Palmer, 2023). It was due in part to this that all 9 of the dead trees reported on quadrat B were Ash. Age estimations were also done on site (refer to Table 9 in appendix) and allowed for estimations across quadrats to determine their respective general ages (see Figure 7). There is extreme difference between the quadrats, as B has overwhelmingly old trees, but they do not make up the majority of trees in the quadrat as its average age lies only slightly above that of the others. The next oldest is quadrat E, which subsequently has the youngest growth of the quadrats.

Soil surveying was used to evaluate the types of soil and their qualities (refer to Table 10 in appendix). A comparison of quadrats B and C (see Table 2) shows that though there is significance in the moisture content which in turn explains the difference in consistency between the two quadrats' soil. Quadrat C also has slightly higher organic content. Note of the man-made in-filled ditches, as part of one exists in Quadrat B and could affect the penetrometer data (see Table 3).

Pollen analysis of Mead Lake, located close in relation to CHS, allows for grouping of most common species of each type of vegetation. In the tree category, alder had long dominated the field, with fluctuations leading to its ultimate end in the most recent zone, leading to a correlated increase in all other species listed in the diagram. Shrubs have significantly seen only two species. Hazel is seen swinging around the entirety of the graph, while willow has a

short-lived interruption in the middle. Grass completely dominates the entire herbs subsection.

Water quality analysis from the sampling sites (see Figure 10) demonstrates very little statistical significance other than those seen in dissolved oxygen, conductivity, and nitrates (see Figure 9). The data (refer to Table 10) was taken before any possibly statistically significant weather alterations. It is also important to note that tap water phosphates are above the threshold due to the threshold being for natural, unpurified water sources.

FREQUENCY OF TREE TYPES IN QUADRATS A-E OF COOPER'S HILL SLOPES

Figure 6: Frequency of tree species in CHS

Figure 7: Age of trees in CHS by quadrat

Quadrat Soil Sample	Texture	Colour	Roots	Structure	Consistency	pH	% Moisture Content	% Organic Content
B topsoil	Sandy loam	10YR 3/2 very dark grayish brown	common	Moderately developed, subangular peds	friable	4.92	5.97	2.46
B subsoil	Silt clay loam	10YR 3/3 dark brown	few	Moderate/strongly developed, subangular peds	friable	4.82	4.01	2.04

Figure 9: Water quality measurements. Threshold data source: CONAMA (2005), referenced in Lorrane de Oliveira, Ramos *et.al* (2020), posted in Reasearch Gate (2020)

Figure 10: Water quality sampling locations. (Palmer 2023)

Discussion

In terms of past land-use, CHS can be defined by its vegetation, soil, and pollen data. This history of CHS's land-use can be seen in recorded maps from various times. Figure 11 shows CHS in 1881, and though it is grainy, the sampling site can be found by intersecting down from the 'e' in 'River' of 'River Thames' and across from the map stamp titled 'Runnymede'. The area made up of two small rectangular shapes, is shown unshaded and white, signalling absence of vegetation. This is true as well in the 1930 map, see Figure 12, but changes come in the map of 1960, see Figure 13. In this map, the area is dotted with vegetation showing perhaps a change in land-use. The map in 1970, see Figure 14, continues the trend with a slight visible increase in vegetation identifiers. The gap between Figure 12 and 13, which shows the vegetation change, is the same time the NT began their stewardship of the land, further supporting a change in land-use on CHS (NT Heritage Records). Simultaneously, vegetation age, see Figure 7, estimated from current trees, demonstrates, in comparison with the locations and features of quadrats, see Figure 5, that CHS was likely a farm before it was handed over to the NT. The large oaks which date back to before the NT ownership, and the straight line spacing of the oaks near to the property's borders, makes it clear that CHS has a history of farming. Additionally, the location of vegetation and knowledge of the history of croplands could hint to soil erosion, explaining the rapid drops in the landscape, see Figure 5. These steep slopes are discussed as well in one study, which summarised that some additional common themes of past agricultural use are also only clay-rich, reddish soil, as well as friable or fragile and thin soil, all of which can be seen in Table 2 (Bell, Boardman 1992). Finally, the pollen data, see Figure 8, displays Zone 5, and migration away from herb dominated relevantly revealing the increase in trees and shrubs, likely due to considerable decrease in herbs. This increase in trees does not however account for the loss of ash which can instead be attributed to the blight which is due to human movement (Palmer 2023). In retrospect, the data collected from Mead Lake could have been more accurately measured if, as in Wright (2003), multiple cores had been taken and averaged, rather than depending wholly on one sample to represent accurately the entire body of water. This could be argued for the Langham Pond water quality samples as well due to Langham Pond's long shape and due to this, likely large catchment in comparison to its size.

Figure 11: CHS 1881

Figure 12: CHS 1930

Figure 13: CHS 1960

Figure 14: CHS 1970

Another aspect of CHS is present-day land-use, as seen in the topography and associated field observations. The man-made paths and fences are signs of human activity, and the ash felling previously mentioned. Some species like hazel, are coppiced (National Trust). However, the NT uses these felled or coppiced trees to border off areas in which Palmer (2023) states, there is trace of mountain bikers, which have shown to increase soil erosion in some places (National Trust). The deciduous forest, see Figure 6, also exhibits ditches which have been filled, possibly affecting penetrometer data, see Table 3. This disruption of soil gradient can cause ‘alteration of hydrological flow paths’ outlined by Holden *et al.* (2016, pp. 526), this is particularly dangerous on CHS with increasing human development above the slopes, see Figure 1, and the floodplain below. CHS contributes to the ground water aspect of the Thames’ water table, making it necessary for good cleansing of human or other pollutants, to keep the Thames unaffected. The water quality, see Figure 9, is another factor affected by present land-use practices. Both the pH and ammonia levels of the samples are within the safe threshold, and are statistically similar. pH is most affected by human factors such as increased erosion, pollutants, and especially eutrophication. While above natural levels of ammonia can be attributed to faecal pollution, unless in some cases of drinking water, in which case the addition of ammonia is a stage in sanitation processes (WHO 2003). However, the dissolved oxygen content of the pond and lake is significantly lower than that of the tap water, due to the lack of movement in pond water especially, allowing for less air to pass into water layers. Daniel *et al.* (2002) linked dissolved oxygen and conductivity together in a study of sewage in river systems, it is likely that the river sample has a higher conductivity and lower dissolved oxygen rate due to the movement of the river water and possible contamination. Additionally, nitrate levels, though below threshold, are high in the river water due to fertilisation run-off, and high in tap water due to similar cleansing processes as ammonia (DWI). Further fertilization can be observed in Figure 15 through phosphate levels, consequently, the catchment of the river sample explains the increase in river over pond levels. The comparison between the samples produces the conclusion that though the river samples are slightly polluted, CHS is not responsible, and is healthy, due to the current preservation tactics of the NT.

Europe Phosphorus Fertilizer Application

Global Fertilizer and Manure, Version 1

Amount of phosphorus fertilizer applied averaged over all crops within the 0.5 deg grid cell. Grid cell values are expressed in kilograms per hectare (kg/ha) ranging from 0 to 370. The data values were computed by fusing global maps of harvested areas for 175 crops with national information on fertilizer use for each crop.

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Source: Petter, P., and N. Ramankutty, et al. (2010). Global Fertilizer Application and Manure Production.
Data distributed by the NASA Socioeconomic Data and Applications Center (SEDAC). <http://sedac.ciesm.columbia.edu/data/collection/fertilizer-and-manure>

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Figure 15: Phosphorus fertilizer in Europe. Data from Columbia University (2010), referenced in SEDAC (2011)

Magnitude and frequency of change are important in noting human impacts, such as how soil erosion due to agriculture is rapid due to movement of sediments, but soil change is slow (Bell, Boardman 1992). Vegetation change is slow as seen in the years taken to repopulate CHS, see Figures 11-14, to its current frequency and diversity of species, see Figure 6. Pollen change is connected directly with vegetation, but the magnitude of change most recently in the pollen diagram, see Figure 8, tells of the human interference, with increase in trees, and felling of ash due to the blight brought over from Japan (Palmer 2023). In the water samples, as previously mentioned, the size of the Thames' catchment means it is affected by a greater area than the other samples, and will experience greater magnitude of change with low frequency. Meanwhile the pond water would hold a low magnitude of change but with higher frequency as it is more effected by its one locality, meaning for example, recent weather patterns would be reflected in its qualities.

Conclusions

Understanding the risks of human impact, and managing proactively rather than reactively, are the keys to successful land-usage. Most conclusively, CHS land-use has changed from farmland to forested reserve. CHS must continue to be managed by the NT if it is to continue to thrive, but heatwaves and flooding will only increase, causing further displacement of people, threatening the 'nature' of CHS.

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Appendix

Total Station 1 Location No.	Bearing (Hz)	54.17 Plan Distance (HD)	Vertical Difference (VD)	Reduced Level (m OD)	Scaled plan (distance)
1	358	11.78	-1.59	52.58	2.945
2	4	18.98	-2.67	51.50	4.745
3	8	21.882	-3.29	50.88	5.4705
4	10	31.832	-5.472	48.70	7.958
5	10	42.718	-7.116	47.05	10.6795
6	317	11.58	-1.164	53.01	2.895
7	293	17.946	-0.378	53.79	4.4865
8	285	18.83	0.095	54.27	4.7075
9	268	19.69	1.14	55.31	4.9225
10	254	22.94	3.206	57.38	5.735
11	259	28.42	3.3	57.47	7.105
12	266	33.83	2.77	56.94	8.4575
13	311	17.63	-1.393	52.78	4.4075
14	300	16.29	-0.914	53.26	4.0725
15	271	13.214	0.67	54.84	3.3035
16	238	18.18	3.128	57.30	4.545
17	226	13.003	2.74	56.91	3.25075
18	190	13.19	3.73	57.90	3.2975
19	186	21.53	4.75	58.92	5.3825
20	187	33.51	5.87	60.04	8.3775
21	188	38.69	7.7	61.87	9.6725
22	189	43.66	8.88	63.05	10.915
23	272	6.31	0.6	54.77	1.5775
24	268	15.59	0.9	55.07	3.8975
25	268	24.36	1.91	56.08	6.09
26	265	33.575	2.85	57.02	8.39375
27	266	37.95	3.08	57.25	9.4875

28	266	41.77	3.284	57.45	10.4425
29	256	33.51	3.72	57.89	8.3775
30	257	26.59	3.4	57.57	6.6475
31	228	17.56	3.49	57.66	4.39
32	221	14.9	3.386	57.56	3.725
33	219	20.12	4.095	58.27	5.03
34	220	24.39	4.47	58.64	6.0975
35	317	7.27	-0.812	53.36	1.8175
36	309	17.293	-1.331	52.84	4.32325
37	310	24.22	-2.197	51.97	6.055
38	310	34.37	-3.08	51.09	8.5925
39	318	34.37	-3.38	50.79	8.5925
40	327	30.5	-3.74	50.43	7.625
41	328	35.67	-4.93	49.24	8.9175
42	338	28.36	-4.51	49.66	7.09
43	336	36.8	-5.45	48.72	9.2
44	336	18.55	-2.22	51.95	4.6375
45	31	17.02	-1.55	52.62	4.255
46	35	18.59	-2.45	51.72	4.6475
47	45	24.61	-2.76	51.41	6.1525
48	44	31.69	-4.11	50.06	7.9225
49	58	30.7	-2.182	51.99	7.675
50	58	18.86	-1.56	52.61	4.715
QA/ Q1	322	6.278	-0.765	53.41	1.5695
QA/ Q1	349	8.139	-1.61	52.56	2.03475
QA/ Q1	324	19.592	-1.957	52.21	4.898
QA/ Q1	295	14.814	-0.562	53.61	3.7035

Table 4: Total Station elevation data control point 1

Abney Level 1	Control Height = 54.17mOD.	Abney Reading (deg)	Slope Distance (m)	Cosine	Plan		Vertical Difference (m)	Reduced level (mOD)	Scaled plan distance)
					Distance (m)	Sine			
1		-6	15.32	0.9945218954	15.24	-0.1045285	-1.60	52.57	3.81
2		-9	13.93	0.9876883406	13.76	-0.1564345	-2.18	51.99	3.44
3		-1	21.4	0.9998476952	21.40	-0.0174524	-0.37	53.80	5.35
4		-8	15	0.9902680687	14.85	-0.1391731	-2.09	52.08	3.71
5		4	4.16	0.9975640503	4.15	0.0697565	0.29	54.46	1.04
6		3	5.55	0.9986295348	5.54	0.0523360	0.29	54.46	1.39
7		8	9.92	0.9902680687	9.82	0.1391731	1.38	55.55	2.46
8		10	5.75	0.9848077530	5.66	0.1736482	1.00	55.17	1.42
9		11	7.35	0.9816271834	7.21	0.1908090	1.40	55.57	1.80
10		12	13.5	0.9781476007	13.20	0.2079117	2.81	56.98	3.30
11		9	6.55	0.9876883406	6.47	0.1564345	1.02	55.19	1.62

12	84	-4	5.4	0.9975640503	5.39	-0.0697565	-0.38	53.79	1.35
13	42	-6	6.54	0.9945218954	6.50	-0.1045285	-0.68	53.49	1.63
14	44	-5.5	8.5	0.9953961984	8.46	-0.0958458	-0.81	53.36	2.12
15	62	-6.5	9.39	0.9935718557	9.33	-0.1132032	-1.06	53.11	2.33
16	78	-7	10.8	0.9925461516	10.72	-0.1218693	-1.32	52.85	2.68
17	90	-6.5	10.65	0.9935718557	10.58	-0.1132032	-1.21	52.96	2.65
18	106	1	8.61	0.9998476952	8.61	0.0174524	0.15	54.32	2.15
19	107	-1	13.15	0.9998476952	13.15	-0.0174524	-0.23	53.94	3.29
20	124	6	11.59	0.9945218954	11.53	0.1045285	1.21	55.38	2.88

Table 5: Anbey Level elevation data control point 1

Total Station Pt 2		57.91				
Point No.	Bearing (Hz)	Plan Distance (HD)	Vertical Difference (VD)	Reduced Level (m OD)	Scaled plan distance)	
1	34	4.54	0.08	57.99	1.13425	
2	350	13.26	-0.60	57.31	3.314	
3	345	9.57	-0.09	57.82	2.393	
4	11	4.53	0.17	58.08	1.13175	
5	34	7.81	-0.10	57.81	1.95325	
6	49	9.81	0.48	58.39	2.45275	
7	54	7.10	0.01	57.92	1.77575	
8	63	8.88	-0.14	57.77	2.22075	
9	61	13.28	0.98	58.89	3.32	
10	84	9.24	-0.23	57.68	2.31025	
11	95	11.93	-0.37	57.54	2.982	
12	99	14.57	-0.39	57.52	3.6435	
13	112	15.63	-0.19	57.72	3.90775	
14	113	17.75	-0.15	57.76	4.4385	
15	111	16.63	-0.17	57.74	4.15675	
16	113	21.26	-0.16	57.75	5.31525	
17	112	22.84	-0.33	57.58	5.71025	
18	113	24.35	-0.12	57.79	6.08775	
19	117	25.16	-0.12	57.79	6.28925	
20	117	28.24	-0.02	57.90	7.061	
21	114	30.06	-0.16	0	7.5155	
22	117	32.08	0.00	57.91	8.01875	
23	121	26.82	-0.31	57.60	6.7045	
24	124	22.72	-0.30	57.61	5.679	
25	126	17.95	-0.09	57.82	4.48675	
26	136	15.76	0.69	58.60	3.94075	
27	136	14.11	0.48	58.39	3.52725	
28	145	15.90	1.68	59.59	3.97475	
29	146	13.94	1.33	59.24	3.486	

30	159	9.44	1.01	58.92	2.36
31	158	15.78	2.68	60.59	3.94425
32	166	15.69	2.81	60.72	3.92325
33	175	15.47	3.10	61.01	3.8675
34	189	17.25	3.96	61.87	4.3125
35	187	11.00	2.54	60.45	2.749
36	199	15.90	4.06	61.97	3.97575
37	201	11.04	2.78	60.69	2.76075
38	213	16.16	4.14	62.05	4.03975
39	231	14.23	3.60	61.51	3.55625
40	234	18.90	4.67	62.58	4.72575
41	233	24.99	5.63	63.54	6.24825
42	234	29.39	7.38	65.29	7.34775
43	239	29.06	6.87	64.78	7.265
44	239	25.54	5.75	63.66	6.384
45	240	18.41	4.32	62.23	4.60225
46	247	26.18	5.49	63.40	6.54525
47	247	33.48	7.09	65.00	8.369
48	255	26.25	5.13	63.04	6.5635
49	255	19.96	3.83	61.74	4.98925
50	270	23.32	4.05	61.96	5.83
51	259	15.71	3.29	61.20	3.928
52	236	11.32	2.51	60.42	2.83
53	220	8.70	1.64	59.55	2.175
54	170	9.88	1.20	59.11	2.46975
55	178	5.08	0.48	58.39	1.26975
56	164	4.82	0.39	58.30	1.20375
57	219	5.99	0.72	58.63	1.4975
58	243	6.32	0.71	58.62	1.579
59	246	9.14	1.38	59.29	2.28375
60	254	8.84	1.25	59.16	2.209
61	288	5.70	0.23	58.14	1.42375
62	303	6.20	0.25	58.16	1.5495
63	324	4.83	0.10	58.01	1.207
64	319	10.22	0.26	58.17	2.55375
65	268	29.20	4.78	62.69	7.2995
66	237	32.00	7.78	65.69	8.00075
67	225	30.30	7.78	65.69	7.5745
68	114	25.24	-0.08	57.83	6.311
69	117	27.45	-0.04	57.88	6.863
70	114	31.31	-0.25	57.66	7.8275
71	114	34.90	-0.25	57.66	8.72525
72	114	36.28	-0.22	57.69	9.06875
73	118	34.96	0.06	57.97	8.7405
74	118	29.59	0.04	57.95	7.39675

QE / Q5	250	27.93	5.66	63.57	6.9825
QE / Q5	237	35.46	8.85	66.76	8.86375
QD /Q4	40	8.214	-0.203	57.71	2.0535
	57	17.3	-1.907	56.00	4.325
	87	17.54	-0.849	57.06	4.385
	112	8.886	-0.212	57.70	2.2215
QC / Q3	137	17.974	0.951	58.86	4.4935
	108	19.523	-0.289	57.62	4.88075
	115	29.14	-0.093	57.82	7.285
	136	27.355	1.758	59.67	6.83875

Table 6: Total Station elevation data control point 2

Point No.	Bearing (Hz)	Abney Reading (deg)	Slope Distance (m)	Cosine	Plan Distance (m)	Sine	Vertical Difference (m)	Reduced level (mOD)	Scaled plan distance)
1	48	-4.5	4	0.996917	5.00	-0.08	-0.31	57.60	1.249229333
2	48	-2	6	0.999391	7.00	-0.03	-0.21	57.70	1.749847707
3	48	-1.5	7	0.999657	8.00	-0.03	-0.18	57.73	1.999914331
4	48	-2.5	8	0.999048	9.00	-0.04	-0.35	57.56	2.249762055
5	48	-5	10	0.996195	11.00	-0.09	-0.87	57.04	2.749048675
6	48	-5.4	12	0.995562	13.00	-0.09	-1.13	56.78	3.248890491
7	48	-5.6	14	0.995227	15.00	-0.10	-1.37	56.54	3.74880685
8	48	-7	16	0.992546	16.99	-0.12	-1.95	55.96	4.248136538
9	48	-8	18	0.990268	18.99	-0.14	-2.51	55.40	4.747567017
10	48	-9	20	0.987688	20.99	-0.16	-3.13	54.78	5.246922085
11	82	-6	12	0.994522	12.99	-0.10	-1.25	56.66	3.248630474
12	50	-6.5	16	0.993572	16.99	-0.11	-1.81	56.10	4.248392964
13	50	-4	10	0.997564	11.00	-0.07	-0.70	57.21	2.749391013
14	18	-3	8.5	0.998630	9.50	-0.05	-0.44	57.47	2.374657384
15	72	-9	18	0.987688	18.99	-0.16	-2.82	55.09	4.746922085
16	44	-8	22.5	0.990268	23.49	-0.14	-3.13	54.78	5.872567017
17	36	-9	26.5	0.987688	27.49	-0.16	-4.15	53.76	6.871922085
18	32	-7.5	20.5	0.991445	21.49	-0.13	-2.68	55.23	5.372861215
19	18	-5.5	14	0.995396	15.00	-0.10	-1.34		3.74884905
20	20	-2.5	8	0.999048	9.00	-0.04	-0.35	57.56	2.249762055

Table 7: Abney Level elevation data control point 2

Group	Ash/Rowan	Number of Trees									% Bare Ground	Total Number of Trees	Density (m2)
		Oak	Field Maple/Sycamore	Hazel	Birch	Fir	Pine	Yew	Hawthorn/Blackthorn	Other			
A1	8	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5%	9	0.9
B1	3	2	6	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	70%	13	1.3
C1	0	0	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	80%	12	1.2
D1	1	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	70	5	0.5
E1	1	1	7	0	1	0	0	0	0	0		10	1

1	Fre q.	2.6	0.6	6	0.2	0.2	0	0	0	0.2	0	9.8		
A2		9	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5%	10	1
B2		2	2	6	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	60%	12	1.2
C2		0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	15%	6	0.6
D2		1	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	80	7	0.7
E2		1	1	5	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	85	9	0.9
2	Fre q.	2.6	0.6	4.8	0.6		0	0	0	0.2	0	8.8		
A3		9	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3%	10	1
B3		4	2	7	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	65%	16	1.6
C3		0	0	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5%	8	0.8
D3		1	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	75	5	0.5
E3		1	1	8	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	90	11	1.1
3	Fre q.	3	0.6	5.6	0.2	0	0	0	0	0.4	0.2	10		
A4		9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5%	9	0.9
B4		4	2	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	60%	13	1.3
C4		0	0	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	60%	12	1.2
D4		1	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	80%	6	0.6
E4		1	1	8	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	85%	12	1.2
4	Fre q.	3	0.6	6.4	0.2	0	0	0	0	0	0.4	10.4		

Table 8: Frequency and tree count data

Age of Trees		Tree Guide.com	National Parks Age	Age of Trees		Tree Guide.com	National Parks Age
1A				2A			
Tree Species	Circum. (cm)	Age (yr)	Age (yr)	Tree Species	Circum. (cm)	Age (yr)	Age (yr)
Rowan/Ash	81	46	32.4	Rowan	73cm	39	15.6
Rowan/Ash	45	25	18	Rowan	63cm	33	13.2
Rowan/Ash	71	40	28.4	Rowan	50cm	27	10.8
Rowan/Ash	55	31	22	Rowan	25cm	13	5.2
Rowan/Ash	29	16	11.6	Rowan	81cm	43	17.2
Rowan/Ah	91	52	36.4	Rowan	40cm	21	8.4
Rowan/Ash	50	28	20	Rowan	58cm	31	12.4
Rowan/Ash	69	39	27.6	Rowan	36cm	19	7.6
Sycamore	8.5	5	1.8	Rowan	64cm	34	13.6
				Sycamore	4cm	2	0.8
1B				2B			
Tree Species	Circum. (cm)	Age (yr)	Age (yr)	Tree Species	Circum. (cm)	Age (yr)	Age (yr)
Ash	48	3	19.2	Ash	18cm	10	7.2
Hazel	11	6	4.4	Ash	7.5cm	4	3
Oak	342	269	171	Field Maple	50cm	31	18
Ash	27	14	10.8	Field Maple	7cm	4	2.5
Maple	9	5	3.272727273	Field Maple	15cm	9	5.5
Maple	9	5	3.272727273	Field Maple	7cm	4	2.5
Maple	9	5	3.272727273	Field Maple	8cm	5	2.9
Hawthorn	52	27	16	Field Maple	6cm	4	2.2

Maple	15	9	5.454545455	Hazel	12cm	6	4.8
Oak	418	329	209	Oak	341cm	269	170.5
Ash	8	4	3.2	Oak Common Hawthorne	386cm 45cm	304	193
Maple	8	5	2.909090909				
Maple	6.5	4	2.363636364				

Age of Trees		Tree Guide.com	National Parks Age	Age of Trees		Tree Guide.com	National Parks Age
1C				2C			
<i>Tree Species</i>	<i>Circum. (cm)</i>	<i>Age (yr)</i>	<i>Age (yr)</i>	<i>Tree Species</i>	<i>Circum. (cm)</i>	<i>Age (yr)</i>	<i>Age (yr)</i>
Sycamore	34	21	12.36	Sycamore	86	46	31.27
Sycamore	10	6	3.63	Field Maple	57	35	20.73
Sycamore	10	6	3.63	Sycamore	58	33	21.09
Sycamore	10	6	3.63	Sycamore	37	21	13.45
Sycamore	47	29	17.09	Sycamore	13	7	4.72
Sycamore	10	6	3.63	Sycamore	50	29	18.18
Sycamore	10	6	3.63				
Sycamore	10	6	3.63				
Sycamore	50	31	18.18				
Sycamore	55	34	20				
Sycamore	17.5	11	6.36				
Sycamore	64	38	23.27				
1D				2D			
<i>Tree Species</i>	<i>Circum. (cm)</i>	<i>Age (yr)</i>	<i>Age (yr)</i>	<i>Tree Species</i>	<i>Circum. (cm)</i>	<i>Age (yr)</i>	<i>Age (yr)</i>
Sycamore	45	27	16.36363636	ash	154	82	61.6
Sycamore	20	12	7.272727273	sycamore	56	32	20.36
Sycamore	53	32	19.27272727	Sycamore	60	35	21.82
Sycamore	52	32	18.90909091	Sycamore	24	14	8.73
Ash	146	78	58.4	Sycamore	48	28	17.45
				Sycamore	1.5	1	0.55
				Sycamore	1.5	1	0.55

Age of Trees		Tree Guide.com	National Parks Age	Age of Trees		Tree Guide.com	National Parks Age
1E				2E			
<i>Tree Species</i>	<i>Circum. (cm)</i>	<i>Age (yr)</i>	<i>Age (yr)</i>	<i>Tree Species</i>	<i>Circum. (cm)</i>	<i>Age (yr)</i>	<i>Age (yr)</i>
Sycamore	54	33	19.636363	Sycamore	52	32	18.9
Sycamore	4	2	1.454545	Sycamore	4	2	1.5
Oak	289	228	144.5	Oak	286	225	143
Ash	7	4	3.5	Sycamore	13	8	4.7
Sycamore	6	4	2.181818	Sycamore	1	1	0.4
Sycamore	5	3	1.818181	Hazel	27	10	11
Sycamore	3	2	1.090909	Hazel	25	10	10.8
Sycamore	6	4	2.181818	Sycamore	5	3	1.8
Sycamore	12	7	4.363636	Ash	80	42	32
Birch	35	13					

Table 9.1: 1st half tree age data by quadrat

Age of Trees		Tree Guide.com	National Parks Age	Age of Trees		Tree Guide.com	National Parks Age
3A				4A			
<i>Tree Species</i>	<i>Circum. (cm)</i>	<i>Age (yr)</i>	<i>Age (yr)</i>	<i>Tree Species</i>	<i>Circum. (cm)</i>	<i>Age (yr)</i>	<i>Age (yr)</i>
Rowan	75		30	rowan	73		29.2
Rowan	42		16.8	rowan	55		22
Rowan	61		24.4	rowan	46		18.4
Rowan	39		15.6	rowan	61		24.4
Rowan	50		20	rowan	48		19.2
Rowan	82		32.8	rowan	23		9.2
Rowan	26		10.4	rowan	59		23.6
Rowan	62		24.8	rowan	89		35.6
Sycamore	5		1.8	rowan	40		16
Rowan	57		22.8				
3B				4B			
<i>Tree Species</i>	<i>Circum. (cm)</i>	<i>Age (yr)</i>	<i>Age (yr)</i>	<i>Tree Species</i>	<i>Circum. (cm)</i>	<i>Age (yr)</i>	<i>Age (yr)</i>
Ash	17.9		7.16	ash	17.8		7.12
Maple	6.2		2.26	field maple	54		19.64
Hawthorn	47			field maple	15		5.45
Elm	12.9		5.16	Oak	300		150
Ash	13		5.2	Oak	469		234.5
Maple	4		1.45	field maple	9		3.27
Oak	345		172.5	ash	12.6		5.04
Maple	7		2.54	beech	8.6		3.44
Maple	9		3.23	field maple	9		3.27
Maple	7		2.54	field maple	7.5		2.73
Hawthorn	54			field maple	7.2		2.62
Oak	408		204	ash	13		5.2
Ash	5		15	ash	7.6		3.04

Age of Trees		Tree Guide.com	National Parks Age	Age of Trees		Tree Guide.com	National Parks Age
3C				4C			
<i>Tree Species</i>	<i>Circum. (cm)</i>	<i>Age (yr)</i>	<i>Age (yr)</i>	<i>Tree Species</i>	<i>Circum. (cm)</i>	<i>Age (yr)</i>	<i>Age (yr)</i>
Sycamore	12		4.36	Sycamore	12		4.37
Sycamore	36		13.09	Sycamore	51		18.54
Sycamore	10		3.36	Sycamore	62		22.54
Sycamore	9		3.27	Sycamore	67		24.36
Sycamore	50		18.18	Sycamore	40		14.54
Sycamore	81		29.09	Sycamore	46		16.72
Sycamore	69		25.09	Sycamore	47		17.09
Sycamore	7		2.54	Sycamore	9		3.27

				Sycamore	33		12
				Sycamore	9		3.27
				Sycamore	9.5		3.45
				Sycamore	6		2.18
3D				4D			
Tree Species	Circum. (cm)	Age (yr)	Age (yr)	Tree Species	Circum. (cm)	Age (yr)	Age (yr)
Ash	1.5m		60	Ash	145		58
Sycamore	60cm		21.8	Sycamore	54		19.6
Sycamore	60cm		21.8	Sycamore	27		9.8
Sycamore	20cm		7.27	Sycamore	59		21.5
Sycamore	45cm		16.4	Sycamore	57		20.7
				Sycamore	45		16.4

Age of Trees		Tree Guide.com	National Parks Age	Age of Trees		Tree Guide.com	National Parks Age
3E	4E						
Tree Species	Circum. (cm)	Age (yr)	Age (yr)	Tree Species	Circum. (cm)	Age (yr)	Age (yr)
Sycamore	53		19.3	Sycamore	55		20
Oak	286		143	Sycamore	3.5		1.3
Sycamore	1		0.37	Oak	262		131
Sycamore	12		4.37	Sycamore	1		0.4
Sycamore	7		2.54	Sycamore	12		4.4
Sycamore	4		1.46	Sycamore	6		2.2
Ash	85		34	Sycamore	3		1.1
Sycamore	5		1.81	Ash	85		34
Hazel	27		10.8	Elder	15		
Sycamore	3		1.1	Hazel	37		14.8
				Sycamore	5		1.8

Table 9.2: 2nd half of tree age data by quadrat

Group No.: 1									
		Texture	Colour	Roots	Structure	Consistency	lab pH	% MC	% OC
Soil Sample		<i>eg silty loam</i>	<i>eg 10YR 2/1 Black</i>	<i>eg few</i>	<i>development/ shape/size peds</i>	<i>eg moist/dry</i>			
1A	Topsoil	silt loam	10YR 3/3 dark brown	many	moderately developed	moist friable	6.89	9.86	2.28
	Subsoil	silt loam	10YR 3/2 Very dark Grayish Brown	few small	moderately developed peds 1.5-3cm	moist /firm	4.77	4.72	5.65
1B	Topsoil	sandy loam	10YR 3/2 very dark grayish brown	common	moderately developed peds, subangular	friable	4.92	5.97%	
	Subsoil	silty clay loam	10YR 3/3 dark brown	few	moderately-strongly developed, subangular, 2-3mm, 1-2cm	friable	4.82	4.01%	

1C	Topsoil	Silty Clay Loam	5YR2.5/1 Black	Abundant	Weakly developed/ Subangular and Granular/ Mixture of small and large	Moist/ Friable	7.23	32.40 %	9.50%
	Subsoil	silty clay loam	3/2 5YR dark reddish brown	few	moderately developed, subangular, lots of granular material and some larger peds	moist friable	5.22	22.70 %	5.7%
1D	Topsoil	sandy loam	5YR 3/2 Dark Reddish Brown	many	moderately developed, subangular, peds	slightly hard, friable	5.63	27.87 %	14.6
	Subsoil	Silty Clay	10YR 3/4 Dark yellowish Brown	few	moderately developed, subangular	moist, firm	4.87	15.47 %	5.9
1E	Topsoil	Sandy clay loam	10YR 2/2 Dark Brown	Many	Moderately developed peds, angular blocky, 0.5-3cm	Dry, slightly hard	4.6	31.63 %	41%
	Subsoil	Silt loam	10YR 4/6 Dark Yellowish Brown	Common	Strongly developed peds, angular blocky, 2.5-5cm	Dry, hard	4.24	18.85 %	22.22 %

Group No.: 2									
Soil Sample		Texture	Colour	Roots	Structure	Consistency	lab pH	% MC	% OC
		<i>eg silty loam</i>	<i>eg 10YR 2/1 Black</i>	<i>eg few</i>	<i>development/ shape/size peds</i>	<i>eg moist/dry</i>			
2A	Topsoil	Silty silt loam	10YR 3/1 Very Dark Gray	Common	Moderately developed/ subangular, and granular/ 1-2cm size peds	Very friable	5.20	32.86 %	1.58%
	Subsoil	silty clay loam	10YR 3/4 Dark yellowish Brown	Few	Moderately developed/ subangular/ 1cm size peds	Moist, Firm	5.15	23.36 %	
2B	Topsoil	Clay loam	10YR 3/2 Very Dark Grayish Brown	common	Strongly developed/ angular blocky	Very friable	5.02	5.20%	1.90%
	Subsoil	Silty Clay loam	10YR 3/3 Dark Brown	Few small	Strongly Developed / Angular blocky	friable	4.89	5.10%	0.90%
2C	Topsoil	silty clay loam	10YR 3/1 Very Dark Gray	Common	Moderately developed/ Subangular	Moist, Friable	6.4	59.50 %	5.13%
	Subsoil	Clay loam	10YR 3/1 Very Dark Gray	common	Subangular	Moist, Firm	7	53.42	34.25 %
2D	Topsoil	silty clay loam	7.5YR 2.5/2 very dark brown	abundant	strongly developed peds, angular blocky, 2.5-5cm	friable	5.32	41.77	-20.72 error
	Subsoil	Sandy clay	10YR 4/4 Dark Yellowish Brown	many	Moderately developed peds, angular blocky, 0.5-3cm	firm	4.91	24.28	8.05
2E	Topsoil	Sandy clay	10YR 3/3 Dark Brown	Many	Strongly Developed/ Subangular	Moist, Firm	4.46	24.28	33.27
	Subsoil	Sandy clay loam	10YR 4/4 Dark	Common	Strongly Developed/ Angular Blocky	Moist, Firm	3.93	17.69	21.9

			Yellowish Brown					
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Group No.: 3									
		Texture	Colour	Roots	Structure	Consistency	lab pH	% MC	% OC
Soil Sample		<i>eg silty loam</i>	<i>eg 10YR 2/1 Black</i>	<i>eg few</i>	<i>development/ shape/size peds</i>	<i>eg moist/dry</i>			
3A	Topsoil	Silty Clay Loam	10YR 3/2 Very dark greyish brown	few	Pedal soil, moderately developed, angular blocky	very firm/moist	4.74	22.41	5.59
	Subsoil	Silty Clay Loam	2.5Y 3/3 dark olive brown	few	pedal soil, moderately developed, subangular	very firm/moist	3.71	17.83	2.42
3B	Topsoil	silty clay loam	10YR 3/3 Dark Brown	many	Pedal, Moderately Developed, Subangular	Moist & Friable	4.96	18.24	19.18
	Subsoil	sandy loam	10YR 2/2 Very dark brown	few	pedal, strongly developed, sub-angular	moist, very friable	4.83	16.23	4.17
3C	Topsoil	sandy silt loam	5YR2.5/1 Black	common	moderately developed, subangular (few large peds), mostly granular	friable moist	7.44	12.08	2.09
	Subsoil	sandy clay	10YR3/2 very dark greyish brown	few	moderately developed, subangular, peds	friable moist	7.35	9.58	3.03
3D	Topsoil	Silty clay loam	7.5YR 2.5/2 very dark brown	Many	Moderately developed, subangular, granular	Friable moist	5.31	29.59	13.28
	Subsoil	silty clay loam	10 YR 3/3 Dark Brown	Abundant	moderate developed, subangular, (few peds), natural aggregates	very friable	5.21	38.62	17.66
3E	Topsoil	Sandy clay	10YR 3/3 dark brown	Many	Moderately developed, subangular blocky	Slightly hard	4.71	36.98	27.2
	Subsoil	Sandy loam	10YR 4/4 Dark Yellowish Brown	Common	Strongly developed, angular blocky peds	Slightly hard	4.08	19.9	5.99

Group No.: 4									
		Texture	Colour	Roots	Structure	Consistency	lab pH	% MC	% OC
Soil Sample		<i>eg silty loam</i>	<i>eg 10YR 2/1 Black</i>	<i>eg few</i>	<i>development/ shape/size peds</i>	<i>eg moist/dry</i>			
4A	Topsoil	Silt loam	10 YR 2/2 Very Dark Brown	Common	Moderately developed, sub angular	Firm	6.50	32%	8.80
	Subsoil	Silt clay loam	10 YR 4/4 dark yellowish brown	Few	Moderately developed angular blocky	Firm	3.43	20.10%	3.11
4B	Topsoil	sandy clay	10YR 3/2 Very dark greyish brown	many	moderately developed, insular	moist, very friable	4.5	17.20%	5.43%

	Subsoil	silt clay loam	10YR 4/2 dark greyish brown	few	Moderately developed angular blocky	friable	4.68	16.00 %	4.04%
4C	Topsoil	Sandy silt loam	10YR 3/1 Very dark grey	Many	Moderately developed, subangular, mostly granular	Moist, friable	7.45	52.27	22.26
	Subsoil	Sandy clay	5YR 2.5/2 Dark reddish brown	Few	Strongly developed, subangular	Most, firm	7.46	22.26	3.48
4D	Topsoil	Silty clay loam	10YR 3/2 Very dark greyish brown	Many	Moderately developed peds, subangular and granular	Moist, friable	5.18	25.37	11.22
	Subsoil	Silty Clay Loam	10YR 3/3 Dark Brown	many	Strongly developed peds, columnar, subangular	moist→very friable	5.73	23.22	7.65
4E	Topsoil	Sandy loam	10YR 3/2 Very dark greyish brown	Abundant	Moderately developed peds, subangular	moist firm	4.23	24.93	36.64
	Subsoil	Sandy Loam	10YR 4/6 Dark Yellowish Brown	Common	Strongly developed peds, subangular	slightly hard	4.02	13.77	16.62

Table 10: Soil qualities of CHS separated by group and quadrat

Group	pH	Diss. Oxy mg/l	conductivity micros/cm	Phosphate mg/l	Nitrate mg/l	Ammonia mg/l
1A	8.1	9	313	0	0.103	0.02
1B	7.5	9.07	298	0	0.64	0.05
1C	6.91	9.28	310	0.02	0.11	0
1D	7.5	9.4	285.5	0	0.18	0.01
1E	7.55	8.88	276.4	0.03	0.17	0.05
2A	7.52	8.91	282	0.02	0.73	0.05
2B	8.26	8.91	260	0	0.33	0.02
2C	7.38	9.1	310	0	0	0.03
2D	7.7	9.27	291	0	0.58	0.03
2E	7.71	9.24	283.8	0.1	0.21	0.06
3A	8	9.06	299	0.01	0.17	0.03
3B	7.62	9.12	303	0.19	0.175	0.05
3C	6.99	9.23	281	0	0.063	0.02
3D	7.81	9.36	297	0	0.18	0.02
3E	7.68	9.24	294.5	0.04	0.76	0.03
4A	7.5	9.1	301	0	0.247	0.04
4B	7.94	9.2	303	0	0.143	0.05
4C	7.99	9.14	286	0.03	0.07	0.05
4D	7.77	9.28	294	0.02		0.13
4E	7.68	9.35	286.1	0.06	0.28	0.05
Maximum	8.26	9.4	313	0.19	0.76	0.13
Minimum	6.91	8.88	260	0	0	0
Number	20	20	20	20	19	20
Mean	7.66	9.16	292.72	0.03	0.27	0.04

Standard
Deviation 0.33 0.15 12.96 0.05 0.23 0.03

Table 11.1: Pond water quality measurements

Group	pH	Diss. Oxy mg/l	conductivity micros/cm	Phosphate mg/l	Nitrate mg/l	Ammonia mg/l
1A	8.22	8.76	627	0.55	2.37	0.04
1B	8.22	8.91	583	0.7	1.88	0.01
1C	6.99	8.91	628	0.56	3.1	0.11
1D	7.67	9.12	614.5	0.58	4.5	0.03
1E	7.59	9.1	596.8	0.72	5.5	0.01
2A	7.98	8.58	615	0.5	6.8	0.08
2B	8.19	9.02	561	0.65	1	0.01
2C	6.99	8.81	634	0.7	1.4	0.01
2D	7.91	9.1	624	0	0.5	0
2E	7.85	9.06	634.9	0.78	1.3	0.15
3A	7.65	9	607	0.66	5.8	0.2
3B	8.16	8.84	705	0.72	7.6	0.03
3C	7.16	8.99	607	0.67	5	0
3D	7.54	9.11	685	0.64	7.5	0.03
3E	7.86	9.05	543.7	0.24	4.2	0.05
4A	8.1	8.92	623	0.56	4.17	0.03
4B	8.15	8.88	695	0.62	6.8	0.05
4C	7.41	9.04	623	0.64	3.7	0.05
4D	7.88	9.1	641	0.58		0.02
4E	7.7	9.27	610.2	0.67	7.5	0.03
Max	8.22	9.27	705	0.78	7.6	0.2
Min	6.99	8.58	543.7	0	0.5	0
Number	20	20	20	20	19	20
Mean	7.76	8.98	622.91	0.59	4.24	0.05
Standard Deviation	0.39	0.16	39.48	0.18	2.38	0.05

Table 11.2: River water quality measurements

Group	pH	Diss. Oxy mg/l	conductivity micros/cm	Phosphate mg/l	Nitrate mg/l	Ammonia mg/l
1A	7.39	12.92	729	0.98	4.07	0.03
1B	7.63	13.8	635	0.26	1.94	0
1C	6.32	13.64	661	3.4	2.8	0
1D	6.98	12.7	886	2.2	5.3	0
1E	7.35	13.1	620.9	3.4	2.4	0
2A	6.97	13.19	585	2.6	1.48	0.01
2B	7.39	13	594	2.8	4.82	0.01
2C	7.16	13.69	660	2.4	1.5	0
2D	7.48	13.81	653	4.8	1.2	0
2E	7.33	13.41	642.8	2.79	0	0.02

3A	6.98	13.23	630	2	5.15	0.01
3B	6.97	13.05	698	3.1	5.9	0.03
3C	6.79	13.8	650	2.6	3.8	0.01
3D	7.34	13.67	609	3.4	5.8	0.02
3E	7.16	13.88	565.3	7.2	5.3	0.05
4A	7.1	13.03	650	3	3.2	0
4B	7.22	13.26	672	2.7	4.25	0.09
4C	7.67	13.17	625	2.6	5.9	0.12
4D	7.28	13.33	667.5	1	3.7	0
4E	7.27	12.58	648.5	4.6	1.5	0.06
Max	7.67	13.88	886	7.2	5.9	0.12
Min	6.32	12.58	565.3	0.26	0	0
Number	20	20	20	20	20	20
Mean	7.19	13.31	654.10	2.89	3.50	0.02
Standard Deviation	0.31	0.39	66.21	1.49	1.82	0.03

Table 11.3: Tap water quality measurements

Surveying Practical

Section A Week 2:

On Tuesday, we showed you the area of Coopers Hill Slopes where you will sample vegetation and soil for later practicals in Section A. What we want to be able to do though is to position your sampling area in the wider landscape and we want to produce a contour map in order to achieve that. We have shown you two methods of collecting data to produce the contour map and we have data collected from two points on CHS that can be combined to generate a contour map. These two points can be found in the spreadsheet as two separate worksheets labelled 'Point 1' and 'Point 2'.

What we need to do in this practical is:

1. Calculate the reduced levels for the Total Station (TS) and Abney Level (AL) readings at Pt 1 and 2.
2. Identify the data that you will need to produce the contour map.
3. Explain setting up the paper to draw the map and then plot some points using the data.
4. Understand why you might use these technologies to produce a map when other data is available.

Part One:

Calculate the reduced levels for the TS and AL readings at Pt 1 and 2.

Remember that the reduced level is the difference in height between your control (known) point and your unknown point in relation to a datum, which in this case is metres above sea level (masl) or metres ordnance datum (mOD). The Control point 1 is at a height of 54.17 m OD and Control Point 2 is 57.91 m OD (highlighted in pale blue in the spreadsheet; C1). Please note that in the following guidelines where an expression or formula is to be typed into the spreadsheet it is highlighted in bold.

TS Readings:

Calculating the TS reduced levels is relatively easy as you only have one calculation to make. This is because the calculation for the vertical difference is already made by the TS.

1. We can put an equation into the Cell E3 **=C1+D3**. This will add -1.59 m (D3) to 54.17 m (C1) and give us the answer for the reduced level of Location 1.
2. The reason for using the dollar signs is that we want to keep using C1 in all of the calculations that we will make but using a short cut. Select cell E3 and hover over the bottom right-hand corner of the cell. A black cross should appear

when you do this, left click and then drag down the remainder of column E. This should then apply the same equation to all the remaining points in that column. The use of the dollar signs for C1 mean that this cell will always be used but you will notice that the value for column D will incrementally increase by 1 as you move down the column.

3. You now have all the reduced levels calculated for the Point 1 TS. You can repeat this for point 2 in the second spreadsheet.

AL readings: This is more complicated as we have to add in some extra steps calculating the cosine and sine of the angle to generate the plan distance and vertical difference respectively.

4. First in column M3 use the expression `=cos(radians(K3))` and then drag it down to calculate all of the cosine of the angle (in degrees) for all locations.
5. We then calculate the plan distance by multiplying this (M3) by the slope distance to give us our plan distance.
6. Calculate the sine of the angle using `=sin(radians(K3))` in cell O3. Then drag this down for all of the points. The vertical difference is calculated in P3 with the expression `=O3*L3` which is slope distance multiplied by the Sine of the angle to give us vertical difference.
7. We can calculate the reduced level in the same way that we calculated it for the TS see steps 1-3 (above) but use the relevant cell identifiers.

Part 2:

Which Data do I need:

In the spreadsheet the data that you need to draw the contour map is highlighted in green and for each point these are:

- a. Bearing
- b. Plan Distance
- c. Reduced Level

Identify which columns you are going to need to use for drawing the contour map.

Part 3:

Setting up the page for the contour map and draw points.

This part provides advice on producing the contour map that should make it easier to plot the points. You will need a ruler, pencil, protractor and rubber with the data sheets that you have just generated in excel.

Marking CP 1 and setting north with the protractor:

8. Take the sheet of A3 and lay it on the table in landscape (long axis of the paper across the top and bottom). North will be towards the top of the page and south to the bottom.
9. Approximately halfway up the right hand side of the paper, and 9 cm in from the right hand edge put a small cross, writing CP 1 and the altitude of this point next to it.
10. Place the centre of the protractor over CP 1 and align 0° and 180° as north and south (so parallel to the right-hand edge of the page).
11. Mark 0° at the top of the protractor and also do the same for 90°, 180° and 270° (E, S and W respectively). This will allow you to place the protractor in the same place for each location you plot.

Setting the scale:

12. We are going to plot the points at 1: 400 scale as this should get most points onto the map. This means that 1 cm on the map is the equivalent of 400 cm or 4 m on the ground. Therefore, to produce a scale map using our calculated plan distance, we need to divide the plan distance we have calculated in the spreadsheet by a factor of 4 and this will provide our scaled plan distance on the map. In which case all of the plan distances need to be divided by 4 so in the spreadsheet put the following expression into G3 `=C3/4`. Repeat for the other relevant columns in the spreadsheet.

Plotting a point:

13. Place the protractor's centre over CP 1 and realign 0° (north) and ensure that E, S and W are also correctly positioned according to you tick marks.

14. We know that Location 1 is on a bearing of 358° from CP1, so we find 358° on the protractor and put a tick against this point. Take the protractor away.
15. We know that Location 1 is 11.78 m from CP 1 on the ground so on this map that will equate to 2.95 cm on a ruler. So, we align the edge of the ruler with 0 cm over CP1, align the edge of the ruler to bearing 358° and then find 2.95 cm along the edge of the ruler. Mark this point, take the ruler away and write what the reduced level of Location 1 next to the mark that you have made to locate this point.
16. Repeat this process for all the other points for the TS and AL. Perhaps use a different symbol for TS and AL points so that you know which ones are which when the map is complete.
17. When you have finished the points for CP 1, you will need to move onto CP 2 but you need to place CP2 in the correct position on the map. This uses the same process for plotting the points with CP2 being on a bearing of 277° from CP 1 with a plan distance of 75 m or map distance of 75 m divided by 4, which equals 18.75 cm on the map.
18. This will allow you to plot the points from the second spreadsheet for CP 2. But remember after you have located CP2 on the map you will need to reset north etc by placing the protractor over CP2 and aligning north and south toward the top of the map and parallel to the plane that you used for CP1.

Drawing Contour:

A contour is a line that represents points of an equal altitude. In our contour map, we are going to use the 'cloud' of data points that you have plotted to generate our high-resolution representation of the landscape at CHS.

19. Start by identifying the contours that you will need to plot. Do this by finding the altitude of the highest and lowest points and then write out the list of heights at 1 m intervals between these heights. These are the contours that you will need plot.
20. Start with the lowest altitude contour and draw a light pencil line that separates the points that have a lower altitude from those that have a higher altitude than the contour. So if you are plotting a 48 m contour, on one side of the line all of the values should be greater than 48 m and on the other side of the line there should be values less than 48 m.
21. Repeat step 20 for the other contour intervals that you have identified.
22. You will then need to adjust the contour lines as you have probably just sketched a line that is more or less halfway between the points. For example, if you have two points one with a height of 47.50 m and the other of 48.25 m, 48 m contour must lie somewhere on the straight line between these two points, but if we assume a linear slope gradient between these two points the 48 m contour is most likely to be closer to 48.25 m point than the point at 47.50 m. The logic behind this is as follows:
 - a. The difference in height between the two points is 75 cm .
 - b. The change in height between the contour of 48 m and the higher point is 48.25 cm is 25 cm, whilst the change in height between the contour of 48 m and the lower point is 50 cm.
 - c. The proportion of height change between the two points and the contour is effectively 25/75 for the higher point and 50/75 for the lower point.
 - d. In which case the contour should be drawn at 2/3's of the distance from the lower point or 1/3 of the distance to the higher point.
23. If you repeat this assuming a linear gradient between all points either side of the contour, then you will be able to draw a more accurate contour map, and you will be marked for the precision of the map.

Other Information to be included on the map:

This map will be included as pdf in the report and you will submit a hard copy of the A3 map. To create a pdf or tiff take a picture of the map when it is complete and add it as a **Figure** with a **caption** into the report. It should also have a **scale**, **north arrow**, and a **key**. Remember that there is going to be other information that can be included on this map such as the position of the quadrat, a schematic representation of the soil penetrometer readings and where the soil samples were taken from. The position of trees in your vegetation survey can also be placed on the map.

You could also include the position of the main path on the contour map and also include the position of evidence as to the nature of management in the woodland in the present day. Therefore it is important to take notes of features that you observe in the field when you have the opportunity as you can add this information to your map.

Analysing your map:

The data from the map and the contours that you have drawn can also be used to produce a cross-section and place the quadrat on that cross section.

You could also work out the steepest and shallowest gradients.

What is the aspect of the slopes as a whole?

Do changes in the slope gradient impact the type of soil that you observe in your quadrat?

Figure 16: Surveying methods

1

GG1011 Geographical Techniques

Practical Vegetation Survey Week 3:

The aim of this week's practical is to determine the characteristics of the vegetation of the Cooper's Hill Slopes. You will work in the same groups as before. We do not have the means to sample the whole reserve. Instead we will look at the vegetation near the path we surveyed in the first practical.

Quadrat surveys

The quadrats (10 x 10 m) have been marked out and surveyed in so that you can place them on the contour maps. Use the key to identify the trees using the leaves and if you need a bit of help do ask the demonstrators. You will also need to take some samples that allow us to examine the soil properties within the quadrats. This is a group exercise, so all raw data has to be shared between members of each group. Make sure you take particular care to follow the procedures carefully, and enter all data only on the answer sheets. Remember you only have an hour to complete this so make sure you work efficiently as a team.

Vegetation measurements

1) For each of the trees that has a circumference at breast-height equal to or greater than 5cm, collect the following information:

- What species it is (use the TREE SPECIES KEY in the handout). If the species is not on your handout, collect some specimen leaves, and place in a sealed, labelled plastic bag for later identification. On your booking sheet and plastic bag, give it a pseudo-name such as 'Species A'.
- A visual-estimate of its height.
- A measure of its circumference (use the tape).

2) For all the trees with a circumference at breast-height less than 5cm, estimate the total number of individuals shorter than 1m, and the total number taller than 1m.

3) Visually estimate the percentage cover (0-100%) of non-woody vegetation shorter than 1m i.e. the herbaceous undergrowth. Also estimate the percentage cover (0-100%) of bare ground.

4) Note any other features in your quadrat of interest e.g. other plant types, fallen trees etc.

Soil measurements and samples

1) Soil strength – this is measured using the penetrometer. The value you get is the force per base area required to drive the penetrometer into the soil. Randomly take 20 measurements using the penetrometer from within your quadrat.

2) Soil samples – we are going to dig a very small pit in the soil, to extract one topsoil sample and one subsoil sample for next weeks practical. You will be given two sample bags with the group and quadrat name and TS (Topsoil) and SS (subsoil); place an undisturbed soil sample from each horizon into each bag.

You should consider the following after this practical:

What type of vegetation is dominant on CHS in the present day?

What are the characteristics of the soil on CHS? Also consider this after Week 3 practical?

Does the local relief affect the type of vegetation growing on CHS?

In your sample area, what evidence is there for human activity on CHS? If so, what is the nature of this activity

2

QUADRAT DATA

Date:----- Group no.:-----

Group members:----- Quadrat):-----

PENETROMETER READINGS

Quadrat 1

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

11 12 13 14 15 16 17 18 19 20

Quadrat 2

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

11 12 13 14 15 16 17 18 19 20

TOTAL NUMBER OF TREE INDIVIDUALS WITH A CIRCUMFERENCE AT BREAST-HEIGHT LESS THAN 5CM AND SHORTER THAN 1M

Quadrat 1 = Quadrat 2 =

TOTAL NUMBER OF TREE INDIVIDUALS WITH A CIRCUMFERENCE AT BREAST-HEIGHT LESS THAN 5CM AND TALLER THAN 1M

Quadrat 1 = Quadrat 2 =

THE PERCENTAGE COVER (0-100%) OF NON-WOODY VEGETATION SHORTER THAN 1M

Quadrat 1 = Quadrat 2 =

THE PERCENTAGE COVER (0-100%) OF BARE GROUND

Quadrat 1 = Quadrat 2 =

3

VEGETATION BOOKING SHEET

Quadrat

number

Tree number Species name Height (m) Circumference (cm)

Figure 17: Vegetation and soil surveying methods

Week 5: Pollen Analysis

The aim of this week's practical is to reconstruct the past vegetation and thus environment of the Egham area. In this week's practical you will be given training on the various skills needed to identify pollen this will be supported by on-line resources (moodle quiz and instruction document) that will provide information on constructing and interpreting pollen diagrams.

The pollen, which you are going to look at under the microscope, is from a core taken from Meadlake Place, Egham. Although the core represented a history over 10,000 years, you are only going to investigate material representing the last ~3000 years (see Figure 1 below). We will identify pollen from a series of levels or samples that have been extracted from the 36 cm-long sequence. Each sample was taken 3 cm intervals and we will generate sufficient data to create a pollen diagram of the major plant species and how they change through the different levels. We will be able to place this information within a time framework because we know that the samples accumulated up until more or less the years 2010 AD and we also have a radiocarbon age given for the lowest interval of 36 cm of 2700 cal yrs before present. Consequently, we will be able to calculate the age of each of the pollen sample levels that are represented in the diagram.

Common plant types that you might encounter are listed below. There is some additional information concerning the preferred conditions that these flora would grow in. Some of these conditions are rather broad, whilst others have specific tolerances. Use this information to consider what plants were growing on Coopers Hill Slopes at specific time intervals during the past.

1. *Betula* (birch) – usually dominant on light dry soils, prefers open, unshaded conditions and rare on chalk and limestone.
2. *Pinus* (pine) – in the British Isles, only one species immigrated naturally after the last glacial stage, *Pinus sylvestris* (Scots pine), and is common today in the Scottish Highlands, tolerant of peaty soils and rarely competes in mixed woodlands.
3. *Ulmus* (elm) – common in thickets and hedgerows and tends to be restricted to mature soils with rich organic content.
4. *Quercus* (oak) – in Britain there are two dominant species: *Q. robur* (Pedunculate oak) which likes damp, acid soils and is common on alluvium, but avoids peat or limestone soils; *Q. petraea* (Sessile oak) which is widespread and common on mature but acidic soils throughout the British Isles.
5. *Tilia* (lime) – requires calcareous or base-rich and usually mature soils.
6. *Alnus* (alder) – requires wet soil conditions, usually found in wet places in woods such as lakes and streams and common throughout the British Isles.
7. *Corylus* (hazel) – common shrub layer within woods, but may also form pure hazel woods or shrub, common on damp or dry basic to moderately acid soils, and expands after deforestation as it is a strong competitor in open, unshaded conditions.
8. *Salix* (willow) – usually indicates wet conditions, as for alder.
9. *Plantago* (plantain) – a 'weed' plant, and common invader of cultivated land.
10. Herbaceous species (grasses, daisies, sedge etc...) – a variety of herb taxa, many of which are common in cultivated land or pastures, and all of which indicate non-wooded, open conditions.

Assessment

Your completed pollen data and diagram should be included in the final module A submission. You may want to consider the following:

Figure 18: Pollen analysis methods

Week 7 Practical – Water Quality:

This week's practical we will be testing different water samples to determine their characteristics. The water samples will be from Langham Pond (at the base of Coopers Hill), River Thames, and Royal Holloway drinking water. We will be testing the water samples for the following: pH; Dissolved oxygen; Conductivity; Nitrate (NO_3^-); Phosphate (PO_4^{3-}). Ammonia (NH_4^+); We will use a Paqualab, a portable water testing kit which can be used in the field and in the laboratory. The various tests have been set up around the laboratory with instructions. You will be working in your sub-groups that will be led by a demonstrator. Organise yourselves as to who will carry out the various tests and make sure you follow the instructions given to you.

Please remember that in accordance with safety regulations you must wear a laboratory coat in these practical sessions. There will also be no eating or drinking the laboratory as you will be working with chemicals. Complete the following table:

Test/Sample	Langham Pond	River Thames	Tap Water
pH			
Dissolved oxygen (mg l^{-1})			
Conductivity ($\mu\text{s cm}^{-1}$)			
Phosphate* (PO_4^{3-} ; mg l^{-1})			
Nitrate (NO_3^- ; mg l^{-1})			
Ammonia* (NH_4^+ ; mg l^{-1})			

* Filtered samples

When you have completed the tests, please add the data into the spreadsheet that is in Teams. You will see that each group is repeating the analyses and we will be able to assess the repeatability of the analyses by looking at the mean and standard deviation. Use the lecture notes to think about:

1. What might cause variation/similarities in the results from the different tests?
2. How do these compare to limits imposed by the EU and/or the WHO?

Figure 19: Water analysis methods